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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Social media was used to disseminate project activities to general public and target groups as well as a communication tool for team members. The OIKONET Facebook page, complemented by the OIKONET web portal was the preferred channel to reach the general public and interested stakeholders. Event-specific OIKONET blogs (e.g. workshops, international conferences, participatory actions) supplemented the project website. The OIKONET Twitter channel was used to communicate project activities, particularly those which had taken place in conjunction with project events.

A channel was created in YouTube to disseminate lectures, learning resources, recordings of conference presentations as well as summaries of the project outcomes.

Specific Facebook groups were created to serve as communication platforms for some project activities, particularly workshops and learning spaces. Google + was also used for this purpose.

Finally, the project was disseminated among professionals through LinkedIn, and academics and researchers via Researchgate.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

Social web tools (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, blogs, etc.) were used for communication between project partners as well as for contacting the general public and other stakeholders (students, teachers, professionals, local administrators, etc.) about project-relevant topics. A LinkedIn page was created mainly to reach professionals, and the publication of the project in Researchgate was intended to disseminate the project work among the research community.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The Facebook page of the OIKONET project was created and managed by FASTU, and Google+ was started by AAU. Blogs, YouTube and Twitter channels were created and managed by LA SALLE. The LinkedIn page has been curated by UCLan, and LA SALLE posted the project in Researchgate. A number of partners created Facebook groups to support learning activities. Other partners have contributed with contents to the various social web channels.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The dissemination through the social web complements other dissemination activities carried out at the local level (see Deliverable 7.3 “Local media”). Facebook groups were created to support specific learning activities, such as workshops and learning spaces. The videos published in the YouTube channel were used for dissemination purposes and as learning resources. Twitter was used intensively during events such as project meetings, workshops and international conferences. The blogs were created to support OIKONET events, such as international conferences and international workshop (WP4 Pedagogical Activities), and to disseminate to the general public the work carried out in the WP3 Community Participation. Scientific publications which are not subjected to copyright restrictions will be distributed through Researchgate.

3 FACEBOOK PAGE AND GROUPS

Facebook was the most important tool for the dissemination of the project through social media, being widely used by the general public as well as by most project participants.

Facebook was used in two different ways. The main purpose of the Facebook page was to disseminate project activities and results to the general public. Private Facebook groups provided convenient and communication channels for project partners and in project activities involving the public (e.g. students, activity stakeholders) for the specific activity fields (e.g. workshops, learning activities); for general communication within the project, Google+ (see below) was preferred.

3.1 Facebook Page

The Facebook page of the project started on December 2013 (Figure 1).

<https://www.facebook.com/oikonet/timeline>

The results of the evaluation of the Facebook activity are presented in the Deliverable 6.4 “Evaluation of the digital environment”.

Figure 1. Screenshot of OIKONET Facebook page

Another important aspect of the Facebook page is in the promotion of other dissemination tools. For example, the traffic to the OIKONET website, although generated mainly by organic, direct accesses and referrals, is influenced by the social networks as well. According to information provided in Deliverable 6.4, among the social networks, the traffic to the OIKONET website has been generated almost completely by Facebook (64.6%) and Google+ (31.2%), while Twitter has generated only 2.7% of traffic.

At the time of writing this report, the OIKONET Facebook page had 375 likes.

3.2 Facebook Groups

Private Facebook groups were used for collaboration in specific activity fields. They were used to create discussions, promote events and numerous other activities, enabling a number of people to come together online to share information and discuss specific subjects. Several

groups were created during the project (as closed groups) by different partners:

[OIKONET Lisbon Workshop](#) group was created to support the sociable communication around the subject and collaborative activities of the Lisbon workshop. It has 62 members, mostly the teachers and students participating at the workshop.

[OIKONET Workshop Cottbus 2015](#) group was created to support sociable activities and cover any news regarding the preparation and organization of the next OIKONET workshop, which was to take place in Cottbus (Germany), 1st – 6th of June, 2015. The group had 1 administrator, 16 invited members and 88 members, involving project partners from various working groups, as well as the participants outside the consortium interested in the issue of “Growing and shrinking cities”.

[OIKONET Workshop Belgrade 2016](#) group was created to support sociable activities and cover all news and communication regarding the preparation and realization of the last OIKONET workshop, which took place in Belgrade (Serbia), 6th – 11th of June, 2016. The workshop was dedicated to examining strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. These strategies integrate architectural, urban design and urban planning issues to create a multifaceted framework to develop liveable cities. This open FB group has 1 administrator, 105 members and 3 invited members.

[OIKONET - WP4 Pedagogy](#) group was created after the Lisbon workshop in July 2014 with the aim of fostering the communication and knowledge exchange among the members of the working group Pedagogy, in a less formal way. This group has 32 members, 1 administrator and 1 invited member.

Figure 2. Screenshot of OIKONET group: Habitat Regeneration Strategies

[OIKONET: Habitat Regeneration Strategies](#) group is used for the informal communication supporting the development of the collaborative learning activities on the issue of Habitat (or Housing) Regeneration Strategies. The currently private group, involves 1 administrator, 3 invited members and 116 members, was created after the Lisbon workshop, with the aim of

facilitating and making communication more transparent among the participants in the Workspaces creation and maintenance. The group includes the people outside project consortium interested in the subject.

[OIKONET Learning Activities](#) group addresses the social activities mostly of the members of working group Pedagogy. It was created parallel to WP4 – Pedagogy group and was less utilized than the WP4 group. This group has 13 members and 1 administrator.

[The Skopje Participatory Action Workshop](#) group was created for the informal communication supporting the participatory and collaborative activities of the workshop in Skopje. It was created in October 2015 and has 7 administrators and 33 members.

[OIKONET Small is Power](#) (36 members) and [OIKONET Urban Systems / Urban Axes](#) (10 resp. 11 members) and [OIKONET T.O. Elective Group](#) (27 members) Facebook groups are addressing specific pedagogic activities. There are also a few ad-hoc groups with less than 10 members and very limited or no activity.

4 YOUTUBE CHANNEL

A collection of edited videos documenting the various activities of the project partners is available through the [YouTube channel](#) of the project:

www.youtube.com/channel/UCAPmyERBPcDY9LZbLSDVixg

The current video collection consists of 55 videos (see Appendix), which encompass:

- Video lectures
- Conference presentations
- Project outcomes
- Learning resources

Figure 3. Screenshot of OIKONET YouTube channel

5 BLOGS

In the OIKONET project, blogs were used to communicate specific events (e.g. conferences, workshops, participatory actions), and in this sense they supplemented the project web page, adhering to the general layout rules of the project graphics manual, but using specific menus and information structures. They also supported discussion on presented topics. During the project, eight blogs related to the OIKONET project were set up: three blogs for the three International conferences, three blogs for the three International workshops, one blog to support the discussion about the Housing research readers, and one blog for the Community participation actions.

Lisbon workshop: <http://oikonet-lisbonworkshop.blogspot.es/>

Cottbus workshop: <http://oikonet-cottbusworkshop.blogspot.es/>

Belgrade workshop: <http://oikonet-belgradeworkshop.blogspot.es/>

Barcelona international conference: <http://oikonet-conference-barcelona.blogspot.es/>

Bratislava international conference: <http://oikonet-conference-bratislava.blogspot.es/>

Manchester international conference: <http://oikonet-conference-manchester.blogspot.es/>

Housing research readers: <https://oikonet.wordpress.com/2014/12/17/reader1/>

<https://oikonet.wordpress.com/2016/01/18/reader2/>

Community participation action activities in Barcelona, Rimini, Bratislava and Skopje:

<http://oikonet-communityparticipation.blogspot.es/>.

These blogs are accessible to the general public, but only involved project partners and event participants can contribute to their content. For details of the usage of the blogs and evaluation of the activities in particular OIKONET blogs please check D6.4 “Evaluation of the digital environment”.

The screenshot shows the OIKONET Blogs website for the Belgrade Workshop. The header includes the OIKONET logo and the Lifelong Learning Programme logo. The main banner features a cityscape image with the text "BELGRADE WORKSHOP" and "6 – 11 JUNE 2016". Below the banner, the text reads "Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Liveable Cities" and "FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE, SERBIA". The navigation menu includes "HOME", "TIMETABLE", "PROGRAM", "POSTER", and "GROUPS". The "POSTER" section contains the text "A workshop poster can be accessed and downloaded:" and a link to the poster. The "FACEBOOK GROUP" section includes a link "Click to access". The "OIKONET WORKSHOPS" section includes a link "OIKONET - COTTBUS WORKSHOP 2015 Group 10: Proposal Description".

Figure 4. Screenshot of OIKONET Lisbon Workshop blog

6 GOOGLE+

The “OIKONET” [Google+ community](#) was used as a communication platform for the exchange of messages and information among the members of the project partners. It is a private community, similar to the OIKONET Facebook groups, but while those groups are dedicated to specific events or activities, this Google+ community served as a general communication tool. At the end of the project it had 34 members, but only a few of them were really active. Information on the evaluation of the Google+ use can be found in the deliverable 6.4 “Evaluation of the digital environment”.

Figure 5. Screenshot of the OIKONET Google+ community page

In addition to this general Google+ community, three additional Google+ communities were created for the OIKONET project. The “Housing design MOOC” private community was created as a communication platform for the preparation of the [“Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication” MOOC course](#), but it was not really used (for “technical” reasons). The public community [“OIKONET Site Design Workspace 2016”](#) was created as a communication platform for the collaboration between Aalborg University, DK, and Bialystok University of Technology, PL – in this space students uploaded videos and presentations and received comments on their work from professors and fellow students.

The public Google+ community [“OIKONET Student Online Conference 2015”](#) (with 141 members) was founded as the platform for the event organized in collaboration between Aalborg University, Denmark, and BTU Cottbus, Germany – 4th semester students in architecture and urban design from the two universities presented papers and design proposals here. The conference was organized around four topics relating to contemporary housing and urban design: 1. Waterfront Developments. 2. Brownfield redevelopment, 3. Baugruppen (building groups), and 4. New Patterns of Mobility.

Although Google+ can be used as a tool for the general communication of the project, we preferred the more popular Facebook in this role. As a tool for internal communication of the project members its use was limited by the fact that some of the partners had difficulties to use Google+ regularly. The use of Google+ as an open platform to communicate common pedagogical activities was more successful. In this role, its use was similar to that of the OIKODOMOS Workspaces. However, it is less structured and with limited functionality (compared to this specialised pedagogic platform) but the general public can easily access it and so it is really useful also as a dissemination tool.

Figure 6. Screenshot of the “OIKONET Student Online Conference” Google+ community page

7 TWITTER AND LINKEDIN

7.1 Twitter channel

Twitter was used for exchanging short messages between “followers”. [OIKONET Twitter channel](https://twitter.com/OikonetOrg) (<https://twitter.com/OikonetOrg>) was opened on 17th July, 2014 and at the time of finishing this report the channel statistics were 223 tweets, 35 following, 117 followers and 25 likes. More detailed information on the use of Twitter channel can be found in Deliverable 6.4 “Evaluation of the digital environment” – this information includes statistics of the tweets connected to the major project events, number of retweets and favourites and the use of the most popular hashtags.

The activity of this channel was strongly connected to specific events: more than half of the tweets were published during or immediately after the workshops, while others related to the conferences and project meetings. Common hashtags were #OikoWorkshop and #OikoConference (the main and most frequently used hashtag here was of course #Oikonet). The results of the survey about the use and usefulness of social web tools among the partners can be found in Deliverable 6.4 too. This survey shows that Twitter was regularly used only by a very few members of the project partners. Twitter was not a natural social networking tool for most of the OIKONET partners and its promotion and support was necessary, but not very successful. A larger community of followers could help to promote the project in the general public.

Figure 7. Screenshot of the OIKONET Twitter channel

7.2 LinkedIn group

LinkedIn was used only by a few project members. This network maps the professional connections of its members and is more about this contact “mapping” than about message exchange typical for other social web tools, but LinkedIn groups connecting people with similar interests are available too. Such a group was created for the OIKONET project as well, but it

was not really used. Facebook groups and Google+ communities with very similar functionalities were already being used as communication tools and, in any case, project team members were more familiar with Facebook.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the OIKONET LinkedIn group.

7.3 Researchgate

A space has been created in Researchgate to inform the research community about the project results. All partners with an account in this portal have been invited to be member of the group. Publications which are free of copyright restrictions are available in this portal.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the OIKONET project in Researchgate

8 CONCLUSIONS

During the project, we have made use of most of the available social web tools, with different purposes: to support specific project activities, and to disseminate the project work to the general public. Facebook pages and Google+ have been used to support learning activities, to facilitate communication between distant learners, and as collaborative learning environments to bring together students and teachers from different countries. In these constrained environments, it has been possible to exploit the potential of these tools to foster links among learners, and to create a sense of learning community. A similar purpose underpins the blogs created for the international workshops: they served as supplement of the OIKODOMOS Workspaces, in so far as they enabled the publication and commenting of student works in an open environment to which users did not need to register.

With regard to the ongoing and regular dissemination of project activities to external audiences, this task has been mostly undertaken by the project website (www.oikonet.org) and only secondarily by the Facebook page, and by the Twitter channel. Items displayed in the homepage of the web portal were also inserted in the Facebook page. In the adopted communication strategy, the home page of the web portal has become the showcase of project, with the embedded Twitter working as news channel.

APPENDIX A: YOUTUBE CHANNEL

Some representative videos available in the channel are summarized next.

A.1 Video lectures

OIKONET Bratislava Regeneration Strategies. The presentation about the development strategies of the Bratislava and Petržalka large-housing estate, by Prof. Viera Joklova, from the Faculty of Architecture of the Slovak University of Technology. Teachers and students from the Faculty of Architecture VSUACE Volgograd followed the lecture on-line; partners IUG Grenoble and AF Belgrade follow the lecture of-line.

Figure A.1. Screenshot of OIKONET youtube videolecture given by Viera Joklova

OIKONET "CIVIC HOUSING", Presentation by Leandro Madrazo, Angel Martin. Leandro Madrazo and Angel Martin from the School of Architecture La Salle presented the experience of the seminar "Civic Housing" to teachers and students participating in the Illinden workshop, organized by UKIM, Skopje, Macedonia. OIKONET partners from AF-Belgrade and the Facultad de Arquitectura, Santiago de Chile, attended this video lecture as well.

Figure A.2. Screenshot of OIKONET youtube videolecture given by Leandro Madrazo and Angel Cojo

[OIKONET "CIVIC HOUSING": Lecture by Prof. Omayra Rivera.](#) Lecture of Dr. Omayra Rivera, professor from the University of Puerto Rico, on the topic "Participatory methods of communication", presented to participants in the seminar "Civic Housing", at the School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona. Partners from AF-Belgrade were present as well in the session.

Figure A.3. Screenshot of OIKONET youtube videolecture given by Prof. Omayra Rivera.

[OIKONET Lisbon Workshop - "Contemporary Living Patterns", lecture by Sandra Marques Pereira](#)

Video-lecture by Sandra Marques Pereira from ISCTE –IUL Lisbon on “Mass Housing. A conceptual framework”. Lecture supported students to elaborate the task before the Lisbon workshop on Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe.

[Oikonet Lx2014 PreWork VRato May2014](#)

Video lecture by Vasco Rato from ISCTE –IUL Lisbon on “Sustainability and Housing Design.

A brief introduction”. Lecture supported students to elaborate the task before the Lisbon workshop on Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). SCALE MATTERS. Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Daniel Granados, Lecturer, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2015.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). DIVING INTO ARCHITECTURE . Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Pedro García, Lecturer, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2015.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). 'LOST SPACES vs. OPPORTUNITY SPACES'. Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Pere Buil, Lecturer, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2015.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). “DESIGN IS A WAY TO CONDENSE TIME - THE HEXENHAUS CASE”. Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Prof. Anna Bach, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2015.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). ‘DWELLING ON DWELLING’. Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Prof. Carlos Albisu, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2015.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). 'To Dwell is also to Celebrate New Music and Happening at La Ricarda, 1963'. Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Helena Martin Nieva, Lecturer, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2015.

[Thinking Dwelling Program \(2nd edition, 2016\)](#). Presentations given by faculty members at La Salle School of Architecture, in the second edition of the "Thinking Dwelling" program, in September 2016.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). Living in a symphonic score open to a thousand sounds: Walden 7 (1970-75). Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Helena Martin Nieva, Lecturer, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2016.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). RETHINKING THE ROOFTOP. Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Gerardo Wadel, Lecturer, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2016.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). CASA IV. SHADED & SHELTERED. Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Jaime Font, Lecturer, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2016.

[Thinking Dwelling Program, Architecture La Salle](#). DRAWING, DWELLING & THINKING. Presentation within the THINKING DWELLING program by Sebastian Harris, Lecturer, School of Architecture La Salle, September 2016.

Figure A.4. Recorded presentation on the Thinking Dwelling program: "To Dwell is also to Celebrate New Music and Happening at La Ricarda, 1963", by Helena Martin Nieva.

A.2 Conference Presentations

Presentations given at the two international conferences in Barcelona and Bratislava.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona - Ognen Marina](#)

Catalogue of urban initiatives in Skopje: Mapping the civic society". Ognen Marina, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, Faculty of Architecture, Macedonia.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona- Carla Sentieri](#)

"Introduction to Housing: A collaborative learning space on the fundamentals of housing design and representation", by Carla Sentieri, School of Architecture, Universidad Politécnic de Valencia, School of Architecture, Spain; Nadia Charalambous, University of Cyprus; Mirjana Devetakovic, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Architecture, Serbia.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Jim Roche](#)

"Designing and constructing for a sustainable future - community urban housing in timber: Projects by 4th year architecture students at DIT", by Jim Roche, Dublin Institute of Technology-Dublin School of Architecture, Ireland.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona- Maria Zwanenburg](#)

"The effect of resettlement on upward mobility and inclusion of the urban poor in India", by Maria Zwanenburg, Maartje van Eerd, Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, The Netherlands.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Nicolai Steinø](#)

"Teaching parametric urban design in a blended learning format: Entering the pocket university", by Nicolai Steinø, Department of Architecture, Design and Media Technology, Aalborg University, Denmark.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Larisa Kuzina](#)

"Resilient and sustainable housing: Examples of student projects", by Larisa Kuzina, Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Russia.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Omayra Rivera](#)

"Guidelines for community participation in the design of collective housing", by Omayra Rivera, School of Architecture at the Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-](#)

"Community Participation on public space: The case of the municipalities of Santiago, Providencia and Recoleta in the Metropolitan Area of Santiago", by Viviana Fernández, Facultad de Arquitectura y Urbanismo, Universidad de Chile.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Sandra Treija](#)

"Co-operation in Urban Renewal Projects: Students' Participation in Transformation Process of Large-Scale Housing Areas", by Sandra Treija, Edgars Bondars, Uģis Bratuškins, Riga Technical University, Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, Latvia.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona- Leandro Madrazo](#)

Civic Housing: Empowering dwellers to shape their living environments. Leandro Madrazo, Angel Martin, La Salle School of Architecture, Ramon Llull University, Barcelona, Spain; Raül Robert, Sostre Cívic, Barcelona, Spain.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona- Isaiah Oluremi Durosaiye](#)

"Drivers of contemporary housing research", by Karim Hadjri, Isaiah Oluremi Durosaiye, The Grenfell-Baines School of Architecture, Construction and Environment, University of Central Lancashire, United Kingdom.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Ekim Tan](#)

"Negotiation and Design for the Self-Organizing City: A Game-Based Approach to City-Making", by Ekim Tan, Founder of Play the City Studio. First keynote speaker.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-](#)

"Security, hospitality, quality, community: The changing meaning of home", by Claire Lévy-Vroelant, Professor of Sociology, Université de Paris-Saint-Denis, France. Keynote speaker.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Alexandra Paio](#)

"Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe workshop: From collaborative design to digital fabrication", Alexandra Paio, ISCTE- Lisbon University Institute, Portugal.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Gábor Csanádi](#)

"Social sustainability and local housing policy", by Adrienne Csizmady, Gábor Csanádi, Faculty of Social Sciences, ELTE University of Budapest, Hungary.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona-Adriana Diaconu](#)

"A collaborative learning space to study mass housing in Europe", by Adriana Diaconu, Université Pierre Mendès-France, France.

[OIKONET First International Conference "Global Dwelling", Barcelona- Pannel Discussion](#)

Participants: Claire Lévy-Vroelant, Leandro Madrazo, Viviana Fernández, Maria Zwanenburg, Jim Roche

Figure A.5. Screenshot of OIKONET YouTube video from the final panel discussion at the Barcelona conference

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Leandro Madrazo.](#) Introduction of the OIKONET project coordinator, Leandro Madrazo.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Ľubica Vitkova.](#) Welcome speech of the Dean of Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Aseem Inam,](#) “Theories of Practice: from Housing Regeneration to Urban Transformation” by Aseem Inam, Parsons The New School for Design in New York City. Keynote speaker.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Panel Discussion.](#) Panel Discussion and exhibition.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Viviana Fernández Prajoux.](#) “Participation and Gender Dimension in the Neighbourhood Regeneration Programme, Chile”, by Viviana Fernández Prajoux, School of Architecture, Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism, Department of Urbanism, University of Chile, Santiago, Chile.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Richard Hayward.](#) “Le Corbusier’s ‘Machine for Living in’ or Mole’s House in the ‘Wind in the Willows’ – Enabling and Disabling Architectures and Urbanisms”, by Richard Hayward, University of Greenwich, United Kingdom. Keynote speaker.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Ognen Marina.](#) “From Narratives to Strategies: Regeneration through Urban Border Conditions in Skopje”, by Ognen Marina, Marija Mano Velevska, Slobodan Velevski, Faculty of Architecture, University Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, Macedonia.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Filip Tittl.](#) “Housing Estates Transformation: Long-Term Strategy and Small-Scale Interventions. Case Study of Housing Estate Spořilov, Jilemnice, CZ”, by Filip Tittl, David Tichý, Šárka Doležalová, Housing Quality Centre, Prague and Michal Kohout, Czech Technical University in Prague, Faculty of Architecture.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Gregor Herda.](#) The “Housing at the Centre” Approach; by Gregor Herda, UN-Habitat Housing Unit, Nairobi,

Kenya.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Vitkova, Gorner, Kolcunová](#). “Transformation of Mass Housing in Slovakia, Actual Problems and Perspectives”; by Ľubica Vitkova, Karol Görner and Pavlína Kolcunová
Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Bratislava, Slovakia.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Andrzej Tokajuk](#). “Standards of Housing for Rent Built by Municipal Social Building Society in Bialystok (Poland) after 1996”; by Andrzej Tokajuk, Bialystok University of Technology, Faculty of Architecture, Bialystok, Poland.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Gojko Bežovan](#). “What is the Added Value of Public Rental Housing Programme as Social Innovation?”; by Gojko Bežovan and Josip Pandžić, Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Karin Schaeffer](#). “Impacts on the Social Representations of Urban and Architectural Transformations in Renewed Districts in France and Elsewhere”; by Karin Schaeffer, Research laboratory PACTE (Politiques publiques, ACTION politique, Territoires) Pierre Mendès France University in Grenoble – France.

[OIKONET Second International Conference "Global Dwelling", Bratislava - Cristina Romão](#). “The Role of the Architect in Participatory Methodologies”; by Cristina Romão and Alexandra Paio, ISCTE-IUL, Lisbon, Portugal.

[OIKONET Third International Conference “Global Dwelling”, Manchester- Final Panel discussion](#). Closing panel discussion with the participation of Adriana Diaconu, Magda Sibley, Adam Evans, Gojko Bezovan, Leandro Madrazo, and Paul Jones

Figure A.6. Screenshot of OIKONET YouTube video from the final panel discussion at the Manchester conference

A.3 Project outcomes

[OIKONET "CIVIC HOUSING" A summary of the pedagogic process and results](#) This video summarizes the pedagogic experience carried out within the seminar "Civic Housing" at the School of Architecture La Salle during the Fall semester 2013_14. Students from La Salle and members of the association Sostre Cívic participated in a process aimed at involving dwellers in the process of designing their future homes. The video describes the learning design process

which involved both students and dwellers.

Figure A.7. Screenshots of video “Civic housing”

[A video report of the participatory action in Rimini](#) out between June 2013 and April 2014 has been produced by Heriscapè. The purpose of this action was to define strategies to overcome the difficulties that some segments of the population (specially, young people) have to access social housing in a medium-size city. The video documents the stages of the action, with the participation of the civil society representatives.

Figure A.8. Screenshots of video “Rimini participatory action”

[A video report of the participatory action in Bratislava](#), an urban walk in the Zemník area. The purpose of has been to gather the views of experts, municipality, residents, general public, community associations and organizations involved in the development of the Zemník area located at the Danube riverfront, next to the city of Bratislava, Slovakia.

Figure A.9. Screenshots of video “Bratislava participatory action”

A.4 Learning resources

[OIKONET: Workspace resource: LA1 task1 1](#). “Middle-class housing. The Portela development.” A film produced under the research project: “Homes for the biggest number: Lisbon, Luanda, Macao”, by the research team of Ana Var Milheiro and Bruno Ferreira. This video was facilitated to students in preparing the tasks before the Lisbon workshop.

Figure A.10. Screenshot of OIKONET YouTube videolecture about Portela development